

A novel neural interfacing electrode array for electrical stimulation and simultaneous recording of EEG/EMG/ENG

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Abstract: Neural interface is man-made information pathway through which biological nerve system could communicate directly with electromechanical devices including computer, robot and even cyborg. This paper introduces a novel neural interfacing electrode array capable of bidirectional information transmission and multi-signals recording. The novel flexible electrode array with 32 channels enables close-looped control and feedback neural interfacing researches with the capability of both electrical stimulation and simultaneous recording of electroencephalogram (EEG), electromyogram (EMG), electroneurogram (ENG) signals. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurement of the electrode array was carried out to evaluate the electrode array electrochemical performance in the electrophysiology frequency range. Electrical stimulation to peripheral nerve was performed with various stimulation configuration of ENG electrode site pairs to produce distinct activation patterns. Muscle action potentials of the gastrocnemius of the hind limb indicated different configuration of electrode site pairs could generate distinct stimulating effect. In addition, three groups of in vivo experiments were conducted to demonstrate the recording ability of the electrode array for nerve signals. The data from 32 channels verified the effectiveness of this flexible electrode array in simultaneous recording of EEG/EMG/ENG in vivo.

Keywords: Electrode array; Electrical stimulation; Recording; Simultaneous

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of animal models could reasonably provide an imperative assistance for the scientific research of deep understanding and effective therapeutics for human diseases [1-4]. Invasive experiments by implanting electrodes into special sites, such brain, spinal or limb et al., are usually conducted to record more high-quality neural signals. So far, various electrodes have been designed. Sanghoon Lee et al. devised flexible split ring electrodes for selective stimulation and neural recording on peripheral nerves [5]. Sanyuan Chen et al. worked out PEDOT/MWCNT composite film coated microelectrode arrays for neural interface that can record signals of inferior colliculus [6]. Mingde Du et al. designed flexible micropillar electrode arrays for in vivo subdural surface recordings from rat's brain [7]. However, all the above existing designs of electrode are usually used to record neural signals from an independent site. Simultaneity of recording from multi-sites is helpful for mapping of different neural signals, such as EEG from brain, EMG from limb muscles, ENG from peripheral nerves. Therefore, an electrode array for simultaneously

recording EEG/EMG/ENG is necessary.

There are some defects in recording EEG/EMG/ENG simultaneously with different electrodes. Firstly, more electrode arrays need more multiple electrode transform interfaces. The fixed position of the electrode transform interfaces is limited to some popular experimental animal, such as rat, due to the small size of rat's head, which will lead to the interference of different electrode transform interfaces in space. Secondly, although some recording devices implement wireless transmission mode [8] to avoid the limit of space, cannot meet the requirement for high sampling rate for large flux signal recording because of heat. Moreover, electromagnetic interference in wireless transmission may result in the inability to record signals of multiple electrodes at the same time.

In this paper, we designed a novel electrode array with 32 channels that enables us to simultaneously record EEG from brain, EMG from hindlimb muscles and ENG from peripheral nerves in rat. We characterized the impedance of the electrode and analyzed the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. The results show fine electrochemical property in

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impedance. In addition, we also performed neural recordings in a rat model, which verified the feasibility of our electrode array for simultaneously recording the three kinds of nerve signals. Furthermore, we conducted electrical stimulation of peripheral nerve while recording muscle action potentials of the gastrocnemius of the hind limb by BIOPAC Systems. The experimental results suggested different configuration of electrode site pairs could generate distinct stimulating effect on the gastrocnemius.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Electrode array design

In order to reduce the number of transform interfaces of electrodes, it is necessary to integrate three kinds of electrodes into one. There is a homemade electrode array, consisting of thirty-two channels in our lab as shown in Figure1(a). We took this electrode array as the main part. Eight of its channels were selected as EMG and ENG channels, others were selected as EEG channels. In order to avoid the impact on EEG signal acquisition and simplify the circuit design, we selected eight channels on the left-most as the EMG/ENG channels and modified the layout of the electrode array. Moreover, we designed new circuit to meet the requirement of recording three kinds of signals at the same time. The lengths of the body stretched out to record EEG/EMG signals are designed according to the size of commonly used rats, leaving a certain margin to make it available for rats of a certain size range.

Fig. 1 Structure of the novel electrode array. (a) Previous homemade electrode. (b) Novel flexible electrode array. (c-e) Details of the electrode array

The novel model was shown in Fig.1(b). Fig.1(c,d) show the details of the electrode array. Red part means

the upper layer and blue part means the bottom layer. As shown in Fig.1(d,e) the number of the electrode sites on the graph corresponds to the channel number. The electrode sites 5,7 are used for recording EMG of hind limb, electrode sites 2,4,6,8 are used for recording peripheral nerve signals and electrode sites 1,3 are used for recording the EMG around peripheral nerve to reduce the interference of EMG signal when analyzing signals of peripheral nerve. Each recording site has a diameter of 0.5mm. Fig.1e shows the remaining twenty-six electrode sites for recording EEG, electrode site R is the reference electrode and electrode site G is for grounding. Each electrode site is circular with an outer diameter of 1.1mm and an inner through-hole diameter of 0.5mm. Curvilinear design of keep-out layer of the electrode array can protect mice from scratches on edges and corners. The flexibility of the electrode array makes the stretched-out part bend flexibly to fit rats of a certain size range. The body of the electrode array was made of polyimide epoxy resin with thin-film copper conductive traces. A layer of Au was electrodeposited on the surface of all the electrode sites.

B. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

Fig. 2 (a) Test platform. (b) EIS of the electrode array. (c) Impedance of electrode sites at 1 kHz

The performance of neural electrodes is mainly limited by the thermal noise that arises from the impedance at the electrode-electrolyte interface [9]. Neural signals will be overwhelmed when the impedance exceeds 5 MΩ [6,10]. The impedance at the electrode-electrolyte interface is inversely proportional

to the effective electrode area. For this reason, we should consider whether to make efforts to increase effective electrode sites areas for noise reduction. Therefore, we characterized the impedance of the electrode array. Particularly, eight electrode sites for recording EMG and ENG are different from EEG electrode sites.

We used CHI660E Electrochemical Workstation of Shanghai Chenhua Instruments Co., Ltd to carry out the experiment. The EIS of the electrode array were measured by three-electrode system in electrolyte of phosphate buffer solution (PBS). The test platform was shown in Fig.2(a). We used CH111 Ag/AgCl electrode of Shanghai Chenhua Instruments Co., Ltd. as reference electrode, CHI115 large-area platinum electrode as counter electrode and the flexible electrode array we designed as working electrode. Fig.2(b) shows representative EIS of the ENG/EMG electrode sites and the EEG electrode sites. The frequency was varied from 1 Hz to 100 kHz using an AC excitation potential of 10 mV. The results of ENG/EMG electrode sites and the EEG electrode sites both exhibits low impedance and consequently can reflect large enough effective areas of the electrode sites. As shown in Fig.2(c), we summarized the average impedance of two kinds of electrode sites at 1kHz that is the typical frequency of neural biological activity. The average impedance of the two types of electrode sites at 1kHz are respective $1284 \pm 431 \Omega$ and $909 \pm 178 \Omega$. The standard deviation is a little large relative to the mean, which could be due to the contamination on the surface exposed to air. The impedance of these electrode sites were several times lower than many homemade electrodes [6,7], which is thus expected to have small thermal noise in neural activity recordings.

III. RESULTS

All procedures were in accordance with protocols approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee at the Beijing Institute of Technology. Male SD rats between 3 and 4 months old and weighing 250–300 g were used in this study. Animals were kept under controlled temperature and a 12-h light/12-h dark cycle with lights on at 6:00 a.m.

A. Method of electrode array implantation

The rat was anesthetized and fixed to the stereotaxis instrument. The EEG electrode sites were fixed to the brain with nails after drilling holes in the corresponding

Fig. 3 Process of implantation. (a) Subcutaneous cannulation operation. (b) Implanted electrode array after subcutaneous cannulation operation.

position of the rat skull. The head of rat led out the electrode array transform interface to connect data acquisition equipment. Fixation of extended parts of EMG/ENG electrode sites required subcutaneous cannulation. As Fig.3(a) showed, the cannula was slowly inserted from the hind limb incision along the subcutaneous line into the brain incision. ENG part of the electrode array was rolled up by using a enough nylon thread through the reserved holes and then put thread through the cannula. Next, EMG/ENG parts of the electrode array were inserted to the cannula and then pulled the thread from the other end. Consequently EMG/ENG parts of the electrode array were taken to the corresponding position along the cannula. After that, we removed the cannula carefully and cut off unnecessary thread. Fig.3(b) showed the implanted electrode array after subcutaneous cannulation operation. Finally, EMG/ENG parts of the electrode array were fixed in the designated position. Particularly, electrode sites 2,4,6,8 wrapped the peripheral nerve and electrode sites 1,3 on the opposite side were attached to the muscle. Electrode sites 5,7 were fasten to the muscle of hind limb. After the implantation process, we sutured the wound of the rat and injected antibiotics to prevent wound infection.

B. Electrical stimulation

Electrical stimulation of peripheral nerve was conducted while recording muscle action potentials (MAPs) of hind limb by BIOPAC Systems. to verify the electrical stimulation function of the electrode array. The distribution sketch of the ENG electrode sites on peripheral nerve was shown in Fig.4(a-b). We used electrode site pairs Stimulation Electrode Sites 2-4 and 6-8 with stimulation current of 3mA to carry out experiments. We used the manual gear on A-M Systems to apply current pulses. MAPs were evoked along with convulsion of the hind limb of rat and we

used BIOPAC Systems to record corresponding signals of gastrocnemius. Experimental data was processed in Python. Corresponding MAPs of two electrical stimulation experiments were respectively shown in Fig.4(a-b). It indicated that ENG electrode sites are available for electrical stimulation. Moreover, the amplitude of MAPs from electrode site pair 6-8 stimulation experiment was obviously higher than those from electrode pair 2-4 stimulation experiment. This might suggest that the activation of fascicles under the electrode site pair 2-4 and 6-8 activated the gastrocnemius in different degrees. Furthermore, different stimulation sites might activate distinct muscles.

Fig. 4 Distribution of stimulation electrode site pairs and corresponding MAPs of gastrocnemius of hind limb.

C. Neural recording in vivo

The flexibility of the electrode array makes it an attractive candidate for in vivo neural signals recordings. To investigate the quality of neural recordings from the electrode array, we conducted three sets of in vivo experiments and made corresponding recordings by PLEXON in this study. In the first set, rat was stimulated by needling their feet in slightly awake state. In the second set, rat struggled freely in slightly awake state. In the third set, the rat moved freely in awake state. All the experimental data we obtained were processed in software of BRAINSTORM. The experimental data need to be preprocessed. In order to reduce the interference of high and low frequency noise, the band-pass filter of 10 to 200 Hz is used to filter the experimental data. Moreover, the eight electrode sites for recording EMG and peripheral nerve signals are far from the reference electrode site, which made them greatly disturbed by electrocardiogram (ECoG) signals when recording signals. We regarded the electrode site 1 as reference electrode of the eight electrode sites and

made differential processing for the data recorded by the other seven electrode sites.

Fig. 5 Recorded data of 32 channels in three experiments. (a) Slightly awake state with stimulation. (b) Free slightly awake state. (c) Awake state.

Fig.5(a-c) respectively showed the different nerve signals recorded simultaneously in three experiments. The channels number are corresponding to the electrode sites number. In particular, the signal amplitude of channel 1 was reduced by 10 times. However, the amplitudes of channel 1 of the three experiments were still high, which meant that there was interference in signal recording. We suspected that there was a strong possibility of ECoG interference. The amplitudes of the

ENG (channel 2,4,6,8) were at microvolt level. The amplitudes of EMG (channel 5,7) of the hind limb in figure b were obvious lower than them in Fig.5(a,c). Because the rat moved slightly in a slightly awake state without stimulation. EEG (channel 9-32) electrode sites showed good performance in experiments. The responses of different brain regions are diverse and therefore the signals recorded by electrode sites at distinct locations should be various, which was reflected in the recording results of the three experiments. In a word, the flexible electrode array can record neural signals from three distant parts of one same animal model simultaneously.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a novel flexible electrode array for electrical stimulation and simultaneous recording of EEG/EMG/ENG is proposed. The results of EIS show that it has good electrochemical performance in impedance. The stimulation function of the ENG electrode sites was well verified by the electrical stimulation experiments. In the experiments of nerve signals recording in vivo, the electrode array could record three kinds of nerve signals concurrently. However, the recorded ENG and EMG signals exhibited high correlation suggesting potential cross-talking or fusion of multiple signals resulted from the innate limits of the cuff typed electrodes to record peripheral nerve signal. The exact reason needs further investigation. In future research, we will focus on improving the performance of the electrode array in neural recording and pay attention to innovate the material and microstructure of the electrode array.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ablat N, Lv DY, Ren RT, Xiaokaiti Y, Ma X, Zhao X, et al. Neuroprotective Effects of a Standardized Flavonoid Extract from Safflower against a Rotenone-Induced Rat Model of Parkinson's Disease. *Molecules*. 2016;21(9).
- [2] Andrzejewski K, Budzinska K, Zaremba M, Kaczynska K. Hypoxic Ventilatory Response after Dopamine D-2 Receptor Blockade in Unilateral Rat Model of Parkinson's Disease. *Neuroscience*. 2016;316:192-200.
- [3] Alam M, Rumpel R, Jin XX, von Wrangel C, Tschirner SK, Krauss JK, et al. Altered somatosensory cortex neuronal activity in a rat model of Parkinson's disease and levodopa-induced dyskinesias. *Exp Neurol*. 2017;294:19-31.
- [4] Domenici RA, Campos ACP, Maciel ST, Berzuino MB, Hernandes MS, Fonoff ET, et al. Parkinson's disease and pain: Modulation of nociceptive circuitry in a rat model of nigrostriatal lesion. *Exp Neurol*. 2019;315:72-81.
- [5] Lee S, Sheshadri S, Xiang Z, Delgado-Martinez I, Xue N, Sun T, et al. Selective stimulation and neural recording on peripheral nerves using flexible split ring electrodes. *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*. 2017;242:1165-70.
- [6] Chen S, Pei W, Gui Q, Tang R, Chen Y, Zhao S, et al. PEDOT/MWCNT composite film coated microelectrode arrays for neural interface improvement. *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*. 2013;193:141-8.
- [7] Du M, Guan S, Gao L, Lv S, Yang S, Shi J, et al. Flexible Micropillar Electrode Arrays for In Vivo Neural Activity Recordings. *Small*. 2019:e1900582.
- [8] Shon A, Chu JU, Jung J, Kim H, Youn I. An Implantable Wireless Neural Interface System for Simultaneous Recording and Stimulation of Peripheral Nerve with a Single Cuff Electrode. *Sensors-Basel*. 2018;18(1).
- [9] X.Y. Cui, V.A. Lee, Y. Raphael, J.A. Wiler, J.F. Hetke, D.J. Anderson, et al., Surface modification of neural recording electrodes with conducting polymer/biomolecule blends, *Journal of Biomedical Materials Research* 56 (August)(2001) 261–272.
- [10] G. Buzsaki, Large-scale recording of neuronal ensembles, *Nature Neuroscience* 7 (May) (2004) 446–451.